

1 **The regulator of G-protein signaling RGS1 is a marker of transformation in cancer resulting from**
2 **high-risk HPV infection in humans.**

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7 We studied transformation in humans *in vivo* by measuring total transcription in the cervix over the course
8 of transformation resulting from high-risk papillomavirus infection. We report here identification of RGS1 as
9 a marker of transformation *in vivo*. A systems biologic approach to identification of gene targets through
10 study of co-regulated transcriptional networks revealed involvement of RGS1 with adaptive immunity
11 through genes encoding class I and class II MHC receptors including HLA-F, HLA-DPA1, HLA-DQB1,
12 HLA-DMA and HLA-DMB, as well as cell surface receptors CD69, CD74 and IFI16. We describe activation
13 of a G-protein associated molecule during transformation whose mechanism of action supports a
14 biologically significant component to transformation in humans involving the adaptive immune system.
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